

ENHANCING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE ON A TEACHER: KEY APPROACHES AND MODELS FOR TEACHER DEVELOPMENT

Sarsenbaev Ramazan Janabay uli

PhD student at NDPI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534094>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 14th December 2024

Accepted: 19th December 2024

Online: 20th December 2024

KEYWORDS

Professional-pedagogical competence, teacher competence, educational process, professional growth, personal qualities, educational standards.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the key components of professional-pedagogical competence, focusing on its significance for teachers in the context of modern education. It outlines various types of competence required for effective teaching, including special competence, methodological competence, socio-psychological competence, differential-psychological competence, and autopsychological competence. These competences are described as essential for teachers to engage students effectively and improve educational outcomes. The article stresses the importance of continuous professional development and the evolving demands on teachers in response to societal changes.

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ УЧИТЕЛЯ: КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ И МОДЕЛИ РАЗВИТИЯ УЧИТЕЛЯ

Сарсенбаев Рамазан Жанабай улы

Докторант НГПИ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534094>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 14th December 2024

Accepted: 19th December 2024

Online: 20th December 2024

KEYWORDS

Профессионально-педагогическая компетентность, компетентность педагога, образовательный процесс, профессиональный рост, личностные качества, образовательные стандарты.

ABSTRACT

В данной статье рассматриваются основные компоненты профессионально-педагогической компетентности, акцентируется внимание на ее значении для педагогов в контексте современного образования. В ней определены различные виды компетенций, необходимых для эффективного обучения, в том числе специальная компетентность, методическая компетентность, социально-психологическая компетентность, дифференциально-психологическая компетентность, аутопсихологическая компетентность. Эти компетенции описываются как необходимые для эффективного вовлечения учащихся и улучшения результатов обучения учителями. В статье подчеркивается важность непрерывного профессионального развития и требования к

учителям, которые меняются в ответ на изменения в обществе.

O'QITUVCHINING KASBIY KOMPETENTLIGINI OSHIRISH: O'QITUVCHINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ASOSIY YONDASHUVLARI VA MODELLARI

Sarsenbaev Ramazan Janabay o'g'li

NDPI tayanch doktoranti

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534094>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 14th December 2024

Accepted: 19th December 2024

Online: 20th December 2024

KEYWORDS

Kasbiy-pedagogik kompetentlik, o'qituvchining kompetentligi, ta'lim jarayoni, kasbiy o'sish, shaxsiy sifatlar, ta'lim standartlari.

ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada kasbiy-pedagogik kompetentlikning asosiy tarkibiy qismlari muhokama qilinadi, zamonaviy ta'lim sharoitida o'qituvchilar uchun uning ahamiyatiga e'tibor qaratiladi. Unda samarali o'qitish uchun zarur bo'lgan turli xil kompetensiyalar, jumladan, maxsus kompetensiya, metodik kompetensiya, ijtimoiy-psixologik kompetensiya, differensial-psixologik kompetensiya, autopsixologik kompetensiya bayon etilgan. Ushbu kompetensiyalar o'qituvchilar uchun o'quvchilarni samarali jalb qilish va ta'lim natijalarini yaxshilash uchun zarur ekanligi ta'riflanadi. Maqolada uzluksiz malaka oshirishning ahamiyati va jamiyatdagi o'zgarishlarga javoban o'qituvchilarga qo'yiladigan talablar ta'kidlangan.

An analysis of the prospects for the development of modern education convincingly proves that only teachers with high professional competence can effectively solve the problems of secondary and higher education.

The improvement of a specialist's competence in the field of education is becoming increasingly important due to the complexity and expansion of social experience, the emergence of new and diverse forms of obtaining and transforming information, and the increasing level of demands placed on the teacher by society and students.

A teacher's special competence presupposes their high authority as a scientist, as a representative of a particular science. It includes knowledge, awareness, knowledge of a specific science, its methodology, current state and development prospects. This type of competence also includes the ability to apply scientific knowledge, using it as a tool for influencing students.

The methodological competence of the university teacher is aimed at effectively organizing the pedagogical process and creating new teaching technologies.

Socio-psychological competence is closely linked to the culture of pedagogical communication and the general style of professional behavior of the teacher. It is precisely

they that allow him to build his communication with different categories of students in different ways, achieving necessary changes in the system of their orientation, professional readiness, and competence.

A teacher's differential-psychological competence manifests itself in their ability to build the learning process taking into account the individual characteristics of students. To engage each student in active work not only on studying the subject, but also on themselves as a future professional and creative person, the teacher requires knowledge of the psychology of personality and the psychology of activity, mastery of pedagogical research methods.

A teacher's autopsychological competence lies in knowing themselves as a professional, being able to make adjustments to their activities and communication, taking into account their strengths and weaknesses. The high level of this type of competence is manifested in the teacher's ability to take the position of a researcher in relation to themselves, their activities, and their results.

R.A. Islamshin, examining the system of multi-level training for future teachers, identifies the following types of pedagogical competence: methodological, subject-specific, methodological, and psychological-pedagogical (1).

The methodological aspect of competence was first identified by V.A. Slastenin (2) and represents a system of a teacher's motivational and value-based attitude towards knowledge, understanding its relativity, variability, the ability to engage in the process of constant knowledge exchange, and active participation in the process of continuous education.

A new approach to the formation of subject competence, according to V.A. Adolf, is contained in the existing versions of the standards of higher pedagogical and university education, in which great attention is paid to the system of scientific knowledge necessary for a specialist of higher qualification of different statuses (bachelor, master, higher school teacher) (3).

Methodological competence among various types of pedagogical competence occupies one of the leading positions. It to a certain extent integrates the entire system of special scientific, psychological, pedagogical knowledge and skills and has a clearly expressed applied character. Today, a truly competent teacher can be called one who has an extensive system of knowledge, has his own individual style of activity.

Therefore, the essence of psychological and pedagogical competence lies in the systematic unity of the teacher's psychological and pedagogical knowledge, experience, and qualities that allow for effective pedagogical activity, purposeful organization of pedagogical communication processes, as well as the teacher's personal development and improvement.

The insufficient development of a number of aspects of postgraduate education, the growing relevance, the theoretical and practical significance of its provisions, require defining the forms and methods of forming a teacher's psychological and pedagogical competence based on modeling its structure.

Modeling, in the broadest sense of the term, is understood as "researching objects of cognition on their models; constructing and studying models of real objects and phenomena, clarifying the properties of any object, process or phenomenon, i.e. its model, as well as for predicting phenomena of interest to the researcher" (4, p.393). In pedagogy, the point of view of G.M. Andreeva is increasingly recognized, which suggests that the concept of "model"

should be considered as a system whose research serves as a means of obtaining information about another system (5). The theorists in the field of modeling emphasize that models in all cases act as analogies of research objects, that is, they are similar, but not identical to the latter.

The creation of a structure of professional competence allowed the author to develop a system of methods for improving the practical activities of IPC methodologists, based on systematic representations, the principles of professional growth management were formulated, and the relationships between the objects of professional growth management of IPC methodologists were determined.

V.A. Adolf, like some other authors, identifies the following components of a teacher's competence: motivational, goal-setting, personal, and content-operational (6). (Fig. 1).

The motivational component of a teacher's professional competence allows for the identification and subsequent formation of future teachers' positive motivations for productive work, as well as, based on an analysis of the sources of human activity, the motivational forces of their behavior, determining how well they understand the goals of their activity.

The goal-oriented component of a teacher's professional competence serves to structure their activities based on scientific achievements. It is based on the following skills:

- to put the problem and translate it into the system of program tasks;
- effective information synthesis;
- monitor the dynamics of the formation of mental changes in students;
- to design and manage the development of students' potential abilities, both cognitive and operational;
- manage students' learning activities, performing design, reflective and regulatory actions.

Figure 1. The structure of professional-pedagogical competence developed by V.A. Adolf.

The technology of forming a specialist's professional pedagogical competence, their upbringing as a creative individual, can be... "constructed as a process of transforming educational activity into a specialist's professional activity" (7, p. 37).

The following are important directions for the formation of psychological and pedagogical competence:

- activity aimed at studying the system of subject knowledge - educational activity;
- activities that take into account subject and psychological-pedagogical features - research activities;
- activity aimed at forming the personal qualities of a specialist - educational activity;
- activity determined by professional-pedagogical specificity of activity on improvement of qualifications;

Using S.A. Gaponeko's model as a basis for researching the process of forming the psychological and pedagogical competence of a higher school teacher, it is necessary to develop a model for training and a program for methodological, psychological-pedagogical, and organizational support of the educational process in the postgraduate education system, through which it is proposed to train a specialist with higher scientific and pedagogical qualifications.

References:

1. Исламшин Р.А. Научные основы функционирования модели непрерывного образования педагогических кадров: Автореф. дис. ...доктора пед. наук. - Казань, 1996. - 41 с.
2. Слостенин В.А. Формирование личности учителя в процессе профессиональной подготовки. - М., 1986. - 160 с.
3. Адольф В. А. Теоретические основы формирования профессиональной компетентности учителя. Дис. ... доктора пед. наук. - М.: 1998. - 292 с.
4. Большая Советская Энциклопедия (В 30 томах). Изд.3-е. - М.: Советская энциклопедия, 1972. - Т.16. - С.393-394.
5. Лекции по методике конкретных социальных исследований /Под ред. Г.М. Андреевой. - М.: Изд-во Московского университета, 1972. - 202 с.
6. Адольф В. А. Теоретические основы формирования профессиональной компетентности учителя. Дис. ... доктора пед. наук. - М.: 1998. - 292 с.
7. Тумалев В.В. Учительство в ситуаций социальных проблем: Автореф. дис. ... докт. социол. наук. - СПб., 1995. - 40 с.